
MILITARY

NATO AWACS makes historic visit

NATO SHAPE

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By U.S. Air Force Captain Virgil Magee

TEL AVIV, Israel - NATO AWACS recently made history with the first ever trip to Israel as part of the ongoing Mediterranean Dialogue.

Hosted by the Israeli Air Force's Squadron 122 at Lod Air Force Base, the AWACS and her crew were greeted with open arms.

"This is a great opportunity for us to increase our cooperation," said Israeli Col. Eyal Cohen. "Additionally we see this as a learning opportunity for our up and coming leaders." During the one and a half day visit NATO and Israeli crews exchanged detailed briefings on how both sides were trained, organized and equipped.

U.S. Air Force Maj. Gen. Gary Winterberger, SHAPE's Force Commander explained the future of the AWACS. "We are constantly looking at ways to make ourselves better," he said. "Our role is expanding and visits like this will, for sure, make us better."

The general later went on to explain some of the missions the AWACS has been involved with in the past. Missions have included: monitoring the skies during the awarding of the Nobel Peace Prize, the defense of Turkey during Operation Crescent Guard and 368 missions over the United States after NATO invoked the mutual defense clause of the of the North Atlantic Treaty, also known as Article 5.

Winterberger also noted the alliance's open invitation to other Mediterranean Dialogue nations. "We are open to all our Mediterranean [Dialogue] partners," he said. "Israel was simply the first to invite us. There is no doubt in my mind that if others send us an invitation, we will certainly do what we can to make the trip."

During the last few hours of the visit young Israeli troops were given the thrill of a lifetime. The thrill of receiving in-flight familiarization from the AWACS multi-national crew.

Just four years in the air force and three years in her current job as an air defense officer, 1st. Lt. Tamar Tsivion never imagined flying on NATO aircraft. "I learned a lot about NATO and the AWACS, things I never knew," said Tsivion. "The flight and the briefings gave me the big picture. I think it's very important to continue doing things like this in the future."